

Chelle Gentemann - Open Science Works

List of Persistent identifiers for relevant Open Science work:

1. TOPS Open Science 101 modules: <https://zenodo.org/records/10161527>
2. TOPS Open Science 101 slides: <https://zenodo.org/records/12752290>
3. Climate Data Analysis with Xarray: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10578401>
4. Butterfly website <https://nasa-butterfly.github.io/>
5. Science Section of \$200 million dollar NASA proposal:
<https://zenodo.org/records/5120586>
6. The secret to writing a great NASA proposal:
<https://medium.com/nasa-butterfly/how-to-write-a-great-nasa-proposal-2c6010faf7ab>
7. OceanHackWeek: <https://oceanhackweek.org/>
8. AGU workshop tutorial: <https://github.com/pangeo-gallery/osm2020tutorial>
9. PICES workshop tools: <https://github.com/python4oceanography/PICES-tools>
10. Python Tutorial for GHRSSST Science Team:
https://github.com/python4oceanography/ocean_python_tutorial
11. Why NASA and federal agencies are declaring this the Year of Open Science. Nature 613, 217 (2023), DOI: [10.1038/d41586-023-00019-y](https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00019-y).